

Complex C Pictures

Gas Phase

Figures 1, 2 & 3 – C0 complexes (unsubstituted) (L – R) X = H, Br, I

Figures 4, 5 & 6 – 2R-C1 complexes (L – R) X = H, Br, I

Figures 7, 8 & 9 - 2R-C2 complexes (L – R) X = H, Br, I

Figures 10, 11 & 12 – 4R-C1 complexes X = H (L – R) *ortho*-, *meta*-, *para*-substituted

Figures 13, 14, 15 - 4R-C1 complexes X = Br (L – R) *ortho*-, *meta*-, *para*-substituted

Complex C Pictures

Figures **16, 17 & 18** - 4R-C₁ complexes X = I (L – R) *ortho*-, *meta*-, *para*-substituted

Figures **19, 20 & 21** - 4R-C₂ complexes X = H (L – R) *ortho*-, *meta*-, *para*-substituted

Figures **22, 23 & 24** - 4R-C₂ complexes X = Br (L – R) *ortho*-, *meta*-, *para*-substituted

Figures **25, 26 & 27** - 4R-C₂ complexes X = I (L – R) *ortho*-, *meta*-, *para*-substituted

Complex C Pictures

Aqueous Phase

Figures 28, 29 & 30 – C₀ complexes (unsubstituted) (L – R) X = H, Br, I

Figures 31, 32 & 33 – 2R-C₁ complexes (L – R) X = H, Br, I

Figures 34, 35 & 36 - 2R-C₂ complexes (L – R) X = H, Br, I

Figures 37, 38 & 39 - 4R-C₁ complexes X = H (L – R) *ortho*-, *meta*-, *para*-substituted

Figures 40, 41 & 42 - 4R-C₁ complexes X = Br (L – R) *ortho*-, *meta*-, *para*-substituted

Complex C Pictures

Figures 43, 44 & 45 - 4R-C₁ complexes X = I (L - R) *ortho*-, *meta*-, *para*-substituted

Figures 46, 47 & 48 - 4R-C₂ complexes X = H (L - R) *ortho*-, *meta*-, *para*-substituted

Figures 49, 50 & 51 - 4R-C₂ complexes X = Br (L - R) *ortho*-, *meta*-, *para*-substituted

Figures 52, 53 & 54 - 4R-C₂ complexes X = I (L - R) *ortho*-, *meta*-, *para*-substituted